

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS FOR SMART CITIES: THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL ECONOMY IN ITALY

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Summary. *The global digital shift, which is based on the integration of digital and smart technologies in all livelihood spheres, has been evoked by several main factors, including lockdowns and restrictions conditioned by the pandemic and the growing sustainability challenges. Although, at the core of the digital economy lie not simply the novel technological implementations but the realization of their economic effects. Among the variety of innovations propelling digital economy, platforms play an important role in supporting data-driven management and decision-making processes. The platform economy transforms traditional ways of socio-political and economic participation through the expansion of social space and providing access to diverse actors within it. These abilities of platforms ensure their crucial role in the creation and development of smart cities and smart projects, which are significant part of the European national digital economies. In Italy, one of the main roles performed by digital platforms for smart cities is widening participation and citizenship (e-participation and e-citizenship) and enhancing participatory design and planning through electronic tools. The result of this process is the emergence of the novel governance and regulation forms.*

Keywords: *digital economy, digital platform, e-participation, platform economy, smart city.*

РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПЛАТФОРМ ДЛЯ УМНЫХ ГОРОДОВ: КОНТЕКСТ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В ИТАЛИИ

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Аннотация. *Глобальный цифровой сдвиг, который основывается на интеграции умных и цифровых технологий во все сферы жизнедеятельности, вызван несколькими основными факторами, среди которых ограничения обусловленные пандемией и возрастающие вызовы устойчивого развития. Однако, в основе цифровой экономики находится не просто новые технологические внедрения, но реализация их экономических эффектов. Среди множества инноваций, которые приводят в движение цифровую экономику, платформы играют важную роль в обеспечении процессов управления и принятия решений, основанных на использовании данных. Платформенная экономика трансформируют традиционные способы социально-политического и экономического участия через расширение социального пространства и предоставление доступа включенных в него акторов. Эта особенность платформ обеспечивают их ключевую роль в развитии умных городов и умных проектов, которые являются значительной частью национальных цифровых экономик в Европе. В Италии, одной из главных ролей цифровых платформ для умных городов является расширение участия и гражданственности*

(электронные участие и гражданственность) и усиление совместного дизайна и планирования (основанного на совместном участии) через использование электронных инструментов. Результатом этого процесса становится возникновение новых форм управления и государственного регулирования.

Ключевые слова: платформенная экономика, цифровая платформа, цифровая экономика, умный город, электронное участие.

The recent global changes can be conceptualized as the digital shift, or digitalization, and the so-called smart revolution, which are founded on the omnipresent spread and integration of digital technologies in all spheres, in particular various economic sectors. Digital technologies fundamentally change the way socio-economic and institutional actors operate, perform transactions, organize workflows, and deliver value. One of the central elements of the digital shift is data-driven management and decision making. There are various factors behind the digital shift, among which are the recent lockdowns and restrictions conditioned by the pandemic. They have, on the one hand, deepened the separation of nodes of many supply chains and, on the other hand, accelerated their shift to digitalization. However, digital transformations in various sectors are aggravated by their degrees of fragmentation and remaining dependency on physical supply chains. Another crucial factor behind digitalization is the need of urban and rural territories to respond to growing sustainability challenges, which incorporate environmental, social, and economic dimensions. The application of smart technologies to economic operations and activities can not only increase their productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness but also promise to decrease their ecological impact.

However, the digital economy, which is based on the added value brought by the integration of digital technologies, does not appear simply because of their use. Moreover, the digital technologies' employment does not bring the efficiency and effectiveness by itself and not uniformly in all spheres of economic activities. As Auzan underlines, for the creation of digital economy, novel technologies have, firstly, to overcome cultural barriers existing in the society. And secondly, the realization of their economic effect requires the shift in the existing business models in particular and institutions in general [1, p. 13]. In such a way, the integration and use of digital technologies is not a sufficient factor of creating a digital economy. One of the foundational reasons is a realization of economic effect from digital technological applications. The economic effect, in turn, can be achieved by a shift or transformation of the existing institutions and business models [1, p. 13].

Digitalization and digital economy encompasses the integration a variety of digital and smart technologies, such as robotics, artificial intelligence, machine learning, sensors, blockchain, internet of things (IoT) and else. However, one of the most prospective digital innovations for the economic development is a digital platform. It can be understood as a software-based infrastructure, which enables and facilitates social interactions, business transactions, relations, networks and activities. There are different types of platforms (social media platforms, service platforms, and media sharing platforms, etc.), which are a set up of many tools. Due to their abilities to aggregate and operate large amounts of data, it supports management and decision making processes based on information. Also, such platforms provide a wider inclusion and connection of diverse actors, not only those presented previously but also new economic stakeholders and institutional actors, who emerged within the novel order conditioned by the digital shift. Moreover, platforms provide an access to those actors who often cannot physically

participate and who were not considered for inclusion previously. Digital platforms can be defined as ‘elevated structures’ and their ability to ‘open up a space for new forms of exchange that suspended the protocols of previous forms of social interaction, communication, mobility and trade’ [7, p. 14]. In such a way, digital economy based on platforms (or platform economy) transforms usual ways of socio-economic participation in a number of ways through providing access to various economic actors and entities resulting in the wider coverage of both territories and actors (stakeholders). Moreover, the so-called new normal calls for not simply a digital platform but platform strategy, which combines business, technology, and data strategy [2].

One of the greatest manifestations of not simply integration of digital innovations into various livelihood spheres but also their coordination and coherence is the development of smart cities. In a broad sense, a smart city can be defined as ‘a city that prospectively performs its activity in the industrial, educational, citizen participation, and technical infrastructure fields, combining them intelligently to serve its citizens’ [4]. In other words, at the core of a smart city lies citizen inclusion and participation in all processes, which is enabled and supported by smart technologies and data. Smart city combines advantages in improved social resilience, cohesion and livability, as well as positive economic and ecological effects. Digital technologies can change the use models and the governance processes since ‘the “smart city” directs investments in both tangible and intangible communication infrastructures, concerning the human and social capital, to achieve a better quality of life and long-term sustainability in urban development’ [3]. While originally the concept focused on a city form, now academics and policy makers also refer to ‘smart region’ and ‘smart territory’¹.

The concept of smart city is an economic and organizational innovation, which provides with the new forms of cooperation among the governmental bodies, private business, and public organizations, new services supported by technologies, as well as novel financial models of private – public partnerships [6, p. 43]. It transforms the governance by the unification of diverse development factors into one system, which is facilitated by more efficient integrated physical and digital infrastructures. In turn, they create a unified digital space with a shared common logic and logistics of flows. The ‘smartness’ in smart cities and regions is built upon, first of all, the use of internet of things (IoT) and information and communication technologies (ICT). Although, an important role in developing ‘smartness’ is performed by digital platforms which integrate tools and technologies for data-driven management, planning, e-participation, and provide with novel operational models. To put in other words, a major part of smart cities’ infrastructural capacities is based on the effective integration of digital platforms.

The development of smart cities is an integral part of the recent digital economic policies and strategies in the European Union. As the third largest economy in the EU, the role of Italy’s progress in building both the national and the union’s digital economy cannot be underestimated. According to the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2022 report, ‘in recent years, digital issues have gained political traction notably with the establishment of a ministry responsible for digital affairs, the adoption of several key strategies and the launch of many policy measures’ [5]. However, the country has still a number of gaps to overcome on the way to a nationally embracing digital transformation. In 2022, Italy was ranked the 18th (out of 27 EU member states) in the DESI report. The Index is composed of four main components: human capital, connectivity, integration of digital technology, and digital public services. While in the field of the integration of digital

¹ In this work, I acknowledge the difference between these concepts but use mostly the concept of ‘smart city’ to refer to the variety of territorial forms.

technology the country shows performance higher than the EU level, the human capital sphere requires significant improvement. One of the largest gaps to overcome for Italy is in the increase of basic digital skills and competencies and the share of digital specialists. Their low rates condition a general low rate of the national digital skills' readiness. This factor, in turn, lies at the core of integration of digital technologies and development of the digital economy in general.

One of the major and prospective paths to build up the digital economy in Italy is strategies to develop smart cities. According to the Smart City Observatory, in Italy the market of Smart City - the "intelligent" and sustainable cities - grew significantly in 2022 (+23% compared to 2021) reaching 900 million Euros, with one in five Italian municipalities launching smart projects last year. Among the Italian most digital cities², the leading positions are held by Florence, Bergamo, Bologna, Cremona, Modena, Roma Capitale and Trento. However, according to the international Smart City Index 2023, only two Italian cities appeared in the top 100 – Bologna and Milan. It is important to underline that, except for the capital city of Rome, there are no highly ranked digital and smart cities in the south of Italy. This manifests a new form of a longstanding divide in the country – the digital divide, with the clusters of the digital and smart growth and specialization located in the North (in particular, Lombardy region) and the central region.

The basis of Italian smart cities are claimed to be inclusive digital innovations - the adoption of technologies that make the administration more effective and efficient, in the perspective of service delivery to citizens and businesses, and that facilitate transparency and civic participation. For their part, engaging citizens and focusing on inclusivity can mobilize communities and bring a wide range of benefits (stronger communities, better services for residents, tackle deprived and disadvantaged neighborhoods, etc.). The leading positions among smart projects are held by those focusing on smart mobility, smart buildings, and analysis of data on tourism, mobility and city events. This reflects the recent, after pandemic restrictions, tendencies towards focus on tourism and touristic mobility across various Italian municipalities.

Furthermore, digitalization and the applications of smart technologies are not spread evenly throughout Italian cities and regions, as was shown. The adequate integration in various operations and interactions and efficiency of smart projects for local and regional processes are sustained or limited by a number of factors, which are often locally determined. A valid project analysis model is based on four variables: the maturity of the municipalities, the maturity of the offer, the use of the data collected and the public-private partnership. The smart projects are often characterized by a poor interconnectivity, on regional and national scopes but also sometimes local. This is rooted, first of all, in the lack of a coherent national strategy of digital transformation and place of smart cities within it, as well as a complex territorial development strategy. Also, the level of maturity of the municipalities is much lower than that of the offer; also the number of public-private collaborations is still too little. The barriers to their development include the lack of sufficient economic and financial resources, adequate digital skills and competencies, and the presence of disparate governance models.

While the embracing development and interconnection of smart cities is still a direction for future policy agenda in Italy, the integration of digital platforms across cities and regions is a more prominent phenomenon. And one of the main roles platforms perform is widening e-participation and enhancing participatory design and planning through novel governance forms (for example, open government and e-governance). In such a way, platforms expand the possibilities of citizens'

² The research conducted annually by FPA (Digital 360 Group) in Italy. It evaluates the digital transformation index of the 108 Italian provincial capitals based on the arithmetic mean of eight indicators.

participation in governance and planning activities through electronic tools. At the same time, they are rooted in the Italian rich and long term experience and traditions of active civil engagement. The current model of civic participation in Italy can be conceptualized as ‘deliberative democracy’, which ‘is essentially based on two crucial aspects that determine, depending on how they are interpreted in practice, the full success of the model: inclusion and deliberation’ [3]. And digital platforms can support and enable both of these aspects, in particular through the implementation of its common logic and mechanisms of coordination and alignment to interactions and transactions. E-participation in planning and governance processes is mostly facilitated by service and social media platforms, which provide, firstly, wider and timely access to a greater amount of services to more diverse groups. Secondly, they facilitate enhancement of social ties and interactions, and exchanges within them, which in turn enable social cohesion and resilience. Nevertheless, a need for a wider spread across the whole country of (local) platforms which represents a particular territory or area and interlinks its variety of stakeholders and networks (social, economic, political, cultural, educational and other), is growing significantly.

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